

STUDIES ON 'LIPASE' FROM OIL SEEDS. PART V. SYNTHESIS OF SOME ESTERS BY LIPASE

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Synthesis of some aliphatic esters by ricinus lipase has been carried out by taking different molecular quantities of acid and alcohol in order to study the effect of change of molecular quantities of the reacting substances on the synthesis of esters.

An attempt has been made to study the effect of change of molecular quantities of alcohol and acid on the synthesis of esters by ricinus lipase by taking at first different molecular quantities of alcohol, keeping the quantity of acid constant, and then different quantities of acid keeping the quantity of alcohol constant.

First of all, the syntheses of aliphatic butyrates as well as amyl formate, acetate, propionate and butyrate were carried out by taking constant amount of acid (0.054 g. mol.) and varying the amount of the alcohol.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

In the first series, each set of the experiments consisted of 0.054 g. mol. of acid and different molecular quantities of different alcohols (*i.e.*, 0.028 g. mol., 0.054 g. mol., and 0.108 g. mol.), 1 g. of lipase, 10 c.c. of ether solvent and a few drops of toluene, and kept in the incubator at 37°. At different intervals of time, 1 c.c. of it was taken, 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol added, warmed and titrated against *N*/10 sodium hydroxide. Always, a blank accompanied the sample. From the difference in readings between the sample and the blank, the percentage synthesis was calculated. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Esters.	Acid=0.054 g. mol.		Alcohol=0.028 g. mol.				
	1st.	2nd.	Percentage synthesis on days.				
			3rd.	4th.	5th.	6th.	7th.
Methyl butyrate	1.1	2.4	3.8	5.0	6.3	7.1	8.8
Ethyl "	0.9	2.0	4.9	7.2	6.8	—	—
<i>n</i> -Propyl "	1.6	3.0	4.2	5.2	7.6	8.2	8.0
<i>iso</i> Propyl "	4.8	8.9	11.2	12.3	14.5	13.8	—
<i>n</i> -Butyl "	5.1	7.2	8.1	10.9	13.2	15.6	14.6
<i>iso</i> Butyl "	6.3	9.5	14.4	15.6	20.2	25.8	24.4
<i>n</i> -Amyl "	12.7	18.6	22.1	28.9	33.2	38.5	37.8
<i>n</i> -Amyl formate	15.2	18.6	21.9	25.6	31.8	36.7	35.8
" acetate	13.1	15.7	17.8	20.8	24.9	27.8	32.8
" propionate	20.2	27.5	35.2	38.5	37.8	—	—
" butyrate	12.7	18.8	22.1	28.9	33.2	39.5	37.8

TABLE I (contd.)

Esters.	Acid=0.054 g. mol.			Alcohol=0.054 g. mol.			
	1st.	2nd.	3rd.	4th.	5th.	6th.	7th.
Methyl butyrate	3.28	4.5	6.9	9.0	11.5	...	...
Ethyl "	3.2	4.2	11.0	15.8	16.5	...	...
<i>n</i> -Propyl "	3.9	4.6	8.2	9.2	15.3	16.9	...
<i>iso</i> Propyl "	11.1	16.0	21.8	22.8	26.8	...	...
<i>n</i> -Butyl "	11.2	13.3	14.8	20.5	24.5	23.3	...
<i>iso</i> Butyl "	14.7	23.4	33.3	42.9	63.4	...	...
<i>n</i> -Amyl "	30.8	55.0	64.9	69.3	78.1	...	...
<i>n</i> -Amyl formate	32.4	40.8	68.6	75.8	78.2	...	...
.. acetate	26.1	32.1	38.7	74.5	83.9	...	...
.. propionate	45.1	55.7	71.2	77.2	76.8	...	...
.. butyrate	30.8	55.0	64.9	69.3	78.1	...	...
	Acid=0.054 g. mol.			Alcohol=0.108 g. mol.			
Methyl butyrate	5.2	7.8	10.2	14.3	12.8	...	...
Ethyl "	4.7	6.8	12.8	17.2	18.5	...	...
<i>n</i> -Propyl "	5.7	7.8	13.9	19.5	23.8	22.8	...
<i>iso</i> Propyl "	10.9	21.8	27.8	29.8	31.6	...	...
<i>n</i> -Butyl "	11.2	15.0	17.8	28.2	35.6	34.8	...
<i>iso</i> Butyl "	15.2	18.9	21.8	29.3	37.8	43.5	...
<i>n</i> -Amyl "	22.8	32.7	48.3	55.6	68.2	79.5	...
<i>n</i> -Amyl formate	28.6	39.8	52.7	68.7	72.8	71.9	...
.. acetate	32.3	37.8	51.7	59.8	65.8	77.9	...
.. propionate	22.1	28.5	37.8	52.3	66.1	75.6	...
.. butyrate	22.8	32.7	48.3	55.6	68.2	79.5	...

In the second series, the synthesis of *n*-amyl butyrate was studied in detail first by keeping the quantity of butyric acid constant and taking different molecular quantities of amyl alcohol and then by keeping the quantity of alcohol constant and taking different molecular quantities of the acid. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Synthesis of n-amyl butyrate.

Alcohol.	Percentage synthesis on the						
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.	7th day.
	Acid=0.054 g. mol.						
0.0108 g. mol.	5.2	6.8	9.5	15.2	16.5	17.8	16.9
0.0370	12.3	17.8	21.8	27.8	31.2	36.5	38.2
0.0540	30.8	55.0	61.9	69.3	76.1	...	...
0.0810	40.2	52.8	59.3	61.8	70.2	76.0	75.8
0.1080	22.8	32.7	48.3	55.6	68.2	79.5	...
0.2160	30.8	40.1	49.8	56.2	72.8	82.5	81.5
0.8480	35.8	45.0	51.2	59.6	68.0	89.8	68.8
1.296	42.3	51.8	62.1	72.8	89.5	91.4	90.8
2.592	50.2	58.9	65.6	79.8	82.1	92.8	90.5

TABLE II (contd.)

Acid.	Percentage synthesis on the						
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.	7th day.
	Alcohol = 0.061 g. mol.						
0.0108 g. mol.	12.8	19.5	28.8	30.2	36.5	35.1	
0.0270	20.2	36.0	41.2	48.0	58.2	57.5	
0.0540	30.8	55.0	64.9	69.3	78.1		
0.0810	32.9	57.9	62.1	68.5	72.8	78.1	75.0
0.1080	36.0	48.2	59.0	65.1	70.9	78.1	79.2
0.2160	40.2	49.0	62.8	66.1	76.2	80.1	79.2
0.6180	28.2	39.8	46.0	50.1	65.7	78.2	81.8
1.296	15.2	36.5	51.9	70.2	81.2	88.5	87.9
2.592	43.8	59.8	65.7	70.9	79.2	89.7	89.7

From Table I it is found that the percentage synthesis of the ester increases in the order : 0.028 g. mol., 0.054 g. mol. and 0.108 g. mol. quantities of alcohol taken for the experiment. In each case (*i.e.*, when molecular quantity is constant) the percentage synthesis increases from methyl to amyl butyrate and the synthesis is always more in the *iso* form than in the *normal* one; further the percentage synthesis is the same when different acids are used.

From Table II it is found that the percentage synthesis goes on increasing as the molecular quantity of either the acid or the alcohol increases till it reaches a maximum value. The maximum percentage synthesis is reached when the concentration of the alcohol or the acid is 2.592 g. mol.

From the above results, it can be concluded that the percentage synthesis increases with the increase in molecular quantities of alcohol or acid taken for the experiment up to a certain limit.